

Comparison of Data Mining Techniques used for Financial Data Analysis

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Abstract— In this paper comparison of different data mining techniques used in financial data analysis is done. Financial data analysis is used in many financial institutes for accurate analysis of customer data to find defaulter and valid customer. In this paper we study about different data mining techniques and further we compare the accuracy of these algorithms by applying on different datasets to find the most consistent and most accurate data mining algorithm

Keywords— Data mining, Bayes Classification, Decision Tree, Boosting, Bagging, Random forest algorithm

I. INTRODUCTION

In Banking Sectors and other such leading organization the accurate assessment of consumer is of uttermost importance. Credit loans and finances have risk of being defaulted. These loans involve large amounts of capital and their non-retrieval can lead to major loss for the financial institution. Therefore, the accurate assessment of the risk involved is a crucial matter for banks and other such organizations. Not only is it important to minimize risk in granting credit but also the errors in declining any valid customer. This is to save the banks from lawsuits. For this purpose we should know which algorithm has highest accuracy.

Loan default risk assessment is one of the crucial issues which financial institutions, particularly banks are faced and determining the effective variables is one of the critical parts in this type of studies. In this Credit scoring is a widely used technique that helps financial institutions evaluates the likelihood for a credit applicant to default on the financial obligation and decide whether to grant credit or not. The precise judgment of the credit worthiness of applicants allows financial institutions to increase the volume of granted credit while minimizing possible losses.

II. DATA MINING TECHNIQUES

Data mining a field at the intersection of computer science and statistics is the process that attempts to discover patterns in large data sets. The overall goal of the data mining process is to extract information from a data set and transform it into an understandable structure for further use.

Aside from the raw analysis step, it involves database and data management aspects, data preprocessing, model and inference considerations, interestingness metrics, complexity considerations, post-processing of discovered structures, visualization, and online updating.

Mostly use Data mining techniques are as follows:

A. Bayes Classification

A Bayes classifier is a simple probabilistic classifier based on applying Bayes' theorem with strong independent assumptions and is particularly suited when the dimensionality of the inputs is high. A naive Bayes classifier assumes that the existence (or nonexistence) of a specific feature of a class is unrelated to the existence (or nonexistence) of any other feature.

Bayesian Algorithm:

1. Order the nodes according to their topological order.
2. Initiate importance function $\Pr^0(X|E)$, the desired number of samples m , the updating interval l , and the score arrays for every node.
3. $k \leftarrow 0$, $T \leftarrow \emptyset$
4. for $i \leftarrow 1$ to m do
5. if $(i \bmod l == 0)$ then
6. $k \leftarrow k+1$
7. update importance function $\Pr^k(X|E)$ based on T
end if
8. $s_i \leftarrow$ generate a sample according to $\Pr^k(X|E)$
9. $T \leftarrow T \cup \{s_i\}$
10. Calculate $\text{Score}(s_i, \Pr(X|E, e), \Pr^k(X|E))$ and add it to the corresponding entry of every array according to the instantiated states.
11. Normalize the score arrays for every node.

The major disadvantage of this model is that the predictive accuracy is highly correlated with this assumption. An advantage of this method is that it requires a small amount of training data to estimate the parameters necessary for classification.

B. Decision Tree

A decision tree is a mapping from observations about an item to conclusion about its target value as a predictive model in data mining and machine learning. Generally, for such tree models, other descriptive names are classification tree (discrete target) or regression tree (continuous target). In these tree structures, the leaf nodes represent classifications, the inner nodes represent the current predictive attributes and branches represent conjunctions of attributions that lead to the final classifications. The popular decision trees algorithms include ID3 (Quinlan, 1986), C4.5 (Quinlan, 1993) which is an extension of ID3 algorithm and CART.

Figure 1- Decision Tree

C. Boosting

The concept of boosting applies to the area of predictive data mining, to generate multiple models or classifiers, and to derive weights to combine the predictions from those models into a single prediction or predicted classification.

Boosting will generate a sequence of classifiers, where each consecutive classifier in the sequence is an "expert" in classifying observations that were not well classified by those preceding it. During deployment (for prediction or classification of new cases), the predictions from the different classifiers can then be combined (e.g., via voting, or some weighted voting procedure) to derive a single best prediction or classification.

The most popular boosting algorithm is AdaBoost (Freund and Schapire, 1996) **AdaBoost**, short for Adaptive Boosting, is a machine learning algorithm, formulated by Yoav Freund and Robert Schapire. It is a meta-algorithm, and can be used in conjunction with many other learning algorithms to improve their performance.

The Boosting Algorithm AdaBoost

Given: $(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_m, y_m); x_i \in X, y_i \in \{-1, 1\}$

Initialize weights $D_1(i) = 1/m$

For $t = 1, \dots, T$:

1. (Call WeakLearn), which returns the weak classifier $h_t : X \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$ with minimum error w.r.t distribution D_t ;
2. Choose $\alpha_t \in \mathbb{R}$,
3. Update

$$D_{t+1}(i) = (D_t(i) \exp(-\alpha_t y_i h_t(x_i))) / Z_t$$

Where Z_t is a normalization factor Chosen so that D_{t+1} is a distribution

Output the strong Classifier

$$H(x) = \text{sign} \left(\sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t h_t(x) \right)$$

D. Bagging

Bagging (Bootstrap aggregating) was proposed by Leo Breiman in 1994 to improve the classification by combining classifications of randomly generated training sets.

Bootstrap aggregating (bagging) is a machine learning ensemble meta-algorithm designed to improve the stability and accuracy of machine learning algorithms used in statistical classification and regression. It also reduces variance and helps to avoid over fitting. Although it is usually applied to decision tree methods, it can be used with any type of method. Bagging is a special case of the model averaging approach.

Bagging leads to "improvements for unstable procedures, which include, for example, neural nets, classification and regression trees, and subset selection in linear regression. On the other hand, it can mildly degrade the performance of stable methods such as K-nearest neighbors.

The Bagging Algorithm

Training phase

1. Initialize the parameter
 - $D = \emptyset$, the ensemble.
 - L_k the number of classifiers to train.
2. For $k=1, \dots, L$
 - Take a bootstrap sample S_k from Z .
 - Build a classifier D_k using S_k as the training set
 - Add the classifier to the current ensemble,
 $D = D \cup D_k$.
3. Return D .

Classification phase

4. Run D_1, \dots, D_k on the input x .
5. The class with the maximum number of votes is chosen as the label for x .

E. Random forest Algorithm

Random forests are an ensemble learning method for classification (and regression) that operate by constructing a multitude of decision trees at training time and outputting the class that is the mode of the classes output by individual trees.

	German Dataset	Australian Dataset	Crx Dataset
No. of Instances	1000	460	690
No. of predictive attributes	20	15	16
Percentage of good credit	70%	60%	44.5%
Percentage of bad credit	30%	40%	55.5%

The algorithm for inducing a random forest was developed by Leo Breiman and Adele Cutler, and "Random Forests" is their trademark.

The term came from random decision forest which was first proposed by Tin Kam Ho of Bell Labs in 1995. It is better to think of random forests as a framework rather than as a particular model. The framework consists of several interchangeable parts which can be mixed and matched to create a large number of particular models, all built around the same central theme. Constructing a model in this framework requires making several choices:

1. The shape of the decision to use in each node.
2. The type of predictor to use in each leaf.
3. The splitting objective to optimize in each node.
4. The method for injecting randomness into the trees.

III. DATASET INFORMATION

Data from the data warehouse about the customers is cleaned and processed. Relevant attributes of the customers required for the data analysis to score their credit behaviour is chosen. We select a good mix of customers who have taken credit of the same type. Meaning they have either take home loans or car loans or credit card. A good mix of customers implies that the data is taken for customers who have repaid the loan immediately or have repaid it after certain amount of delay or have defaulted on the loan. All these types of customers are included in the dataset. The data set excludes any special cases.

The data for each customer is checked for errors. We decide on a certain amount of customers to be included in the dataset. This is so that processing will be easier and creation of a model will not take long. The larger the dataset, more time is required to create the decision tree. It must then also consider all variations in the large dataset decreasing its accuracy. Some public datasets are available on the net at the UCI machine learning repository. Since these are cleaned and scored they are convenient for use with our algorithm. Also, they have been used in the making of other similar algorithms before. Therefore their data's diversity is qualified for thus use.

We have taken three different datasets of different size like small, medium and large dataset. The given below table shows the detailed information of these datasets

IV. COMPARISON

For comparison we apply different data mining on different datasets and check the accuracy of these algorithms.

Following table shows the accuracy of each algorithm on different datasets

Data mining Techniques	% Accuracy		
	Australian Dataset	German Dataset	CRX Dataset
Bayes Classification	85.20%	68.60%	85.40%
Decision Tree	82.20%	63.40%	85.70%
Boosting	82.80%	63.50%	80.90%
Bagging	84.30%	67.60%	85.70%
Random Forest	84.40%	71.80%	86.40%

The given below graph shows the accuracy of different algorithms applied on the Australian dataset. From this, we can say that the Bayes algorithm works better on small datasets.

The given below graph shows the accuracy of different algorithms applied on the CRX dataset. From this, we can say that the Random Forest algorithm works better on medium-sized datasets.

The given below graph shows the accuracy of different algorithms applied on the German dataset. From this, we can say that the Random Forest algorithm works better on large datasets.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The system using data mining for loan Default risk analysis enables the bank to reduce the manual errors involved in the same. From the experiment we conducted, we can conclude that out of these five data mining algorithms we applied on different datasets of different sizes, the Random Forest algorithm is the most consistent and has the highest accuracy compared to others.

Further we can see Boosting has already increased the efficiency of decision trees. The assessment of risk will enable banks to increase profit and can result in reduction of interest rate. The accuracy and efficiency of boosted decision trees in financial data analysis can be improved by integration of domain knowledge.

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